

Factors Affecting Performance and Time Extension of ongoing Construction Projects under Town Development Fund, Nepal

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Abstract

Problems related to performances of the construction projects appear through different directions. Most of the projects fail either in time performance or in cost performance or both. So, the factors assessment in contemporary condition is most. This research was designed to conduct study of ten numbers of under-construction projects funded by German government-owned development bank, KfW (Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau) via TDF. Questionnaire surveys were conducted and examination of records from concerned representatives of the client, consultants and contractors within the research area has been carried out. The factors affecting the overall project performance were ranked using 'five-point' scale ranged from 1 (not important) to 5 (extremely important) and transformed to Relative Importance Index (RII).

All projects under study have been granted extension of time based on the Public Procurement Act (PPA) 2063 and Public Procurement Regulation (PPR) 2064. This study shows material related factors as the most important factors among 8 numbers of groups for time overrun in projects. The potential effect of the time overrun in project is cost overrun followed by arbitration, Litigation, Dispute arousal and Total abandonment. The major factors that affect the performance of the project according to the ranking based on RII value for the perceived view of the client, consultants and the contractors on factors affecting the performance are Design related issues, shortage of materials, Quality related issues, slow decision making, construction methodology, labour supply, payment related issues, site management, discrepancies in contract documents, flaws in organisational structure, interfaces, productivity, change orders, unforeseen site condition, weather conditions and regulatory changes that affect the overall project performance. The major factors identified needs to be addressed to minimize the project time overrun and hence its effects on the Project.

Keywords: Factors, Extension of Time, Effects, Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau

Introduction

Time overrun and cost overrun are critical consequences that are usually imparted due to poor project performance functions in construction of public projects. The study conducted by Mishra and Bhandari (2018) for ten numbers of under-construction projects funded by German government-owned development bank, KfW (Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau) revealed that the cost performance index (CPI) of 8 out of 10 projects is all positive indicating that the projects are within the Budget. Despite of the

price escalation and increasing price of resource each year, the CPI of the projects are within budget. Despite of the price escalation and increasing price of resource each year, the CPI of the projects are within budget. Public entities, especially Government owned entities have common trend to prepare cost estimates of the project keeping themselves in some higher side so as to avoid the cost variation as far as possible.

It is revealed that the Scheduled performance index (SPI) of Office cum Shopping Complex in Byas Municipality,

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Birgunj Bus Park, Birendranagar Bus Park, Bheemdatt Bus Park, Biratnagar Bus Terminal and Nepalgunj Bus Park are 0.12, 0.35, 0.69, 0.23, 0.25 and 0.28 respectively. The SPI with values less than unit indicates the time overrun in the projects. 6 out of 10 projects have passed through time overrun. This research raised a strong demand of identifying the factors and Extension of time process in these projects for assessment. It is just extension of the research conducted by Mishra and Bhandari, (2018). So the objective of the research is to assess Factors Affecting performance and Time Extension of ongoing Construction projects under Town Development Fund, Nepal.

Literature Review

Provision for Time Extension in Public Procurements of Nepal

The sub-clause 27 of the General Conditions of Contract of the Bidding Document for the Procurement of the Works prepared by Public Procurement Monitoring Office of Nepal (2014) has stated that the time can be extended if a Compensation Event occurs or a Variation is issued which makes it impossible for Completion to be achieved by the Intended Completion Date without the Contractor taking steps to accelerate the remaining work, which would cause the Contractor to incur additional cost.

It further mentioned that the Employer has to decide whether and by how much to extend the Intended Completion Date within 21 days of the Contractor asking the Project Manager for a decision upon the effect of a Compensation Event or Variation and submitting full supporting information at least 7 days prior to the intended completion date. If the Contractor has failed to give early warning of a delay or has failed to cooperate in dealing with a delay, the delay by this failure shall not be considered in assessing the new Intended Completion Date.

The Section 56 of the Public Procurement Act of Public Procurement Monitoring Office, (2006) has provisioned for the extension of period of procurement contract. It states that if the period of procurement contract is to be inevitably extended due to force majeure, failure of the Public Entity to make available the materials to be made available by it or other reasonable causes, the competent authority may extend the period on the prescribed grounds upon submission of application by the person obtaining procurement contract.

Further, the section 120 of Public Procurement Monitoring Office (2007) has made elaboration in line with the Sub Clause 56 of the Public Procurement Act of PPMO. It states that If the work under the procurement contract cannot be completed within the time of such a contract due to the occurrence of conditions set out in Section 56 of the Act, the concerned construction entrepreneur, supplier, service

provider or consultant, as the case may be, shall have to make an application, for extension of time, stating reasons thereof, to the concerned Public Entity at least seven days before the time of such contract expires. Section 121 of the Public Procurement Monitoring Office (2007) is related to the Liquidity damages which states that if the work under the procurement contract could not be completed within the time specified in the contract due to the delay of the supplier, consultant, service provider or construction entrepreneur, as the case may be, he/she shall have to pay to the Public Entity liquidated damages, generally of zero decimal zero five (0.05) percent of the contract price per day not exceeding ten percent of the contract price.

Provision for Cost variation in procurement of works in Public Procurements of Nepal

The section 54 of the public procurement Act (2007) is about Variation Order (VO). It states that unless otherwise provided for in the procurement contract, if the circumstances that could not be foreseen at the time of signing of procurement contract arise in the course of implementation of the procurement contract, the competent authority may, by stating clear reasons thereof, issue as prescribed, a variation order for a variation of up to fifteen percent and for a variation order above it, a variation order may be issued as per the decision made by the Government of Nepal Council of Ministers by complying with the procedure as prescribed in the case of the Public Entity

The sub-clause 118 of the Public Procurement Regulation, 2064 (2007) is about variation order. It states that if once a work under a procurement contract has already been started, if alteration in or addition of new item to or replacement to the quantity of such work is required due to technical reasons, the authority may, after preparing the cost estimate of such alteration and new item, issue a variation order as follows, subject to the provision of Section 54 of the act:

- In cases where the drawing, design and specifications etc. of the construction work need not require to be changed but the quantity of the work will be altered, a variation order of up to five percent of the contract price by the chief of the public entity of gazetted second class, by assigning technical justification
- A variation order of up to ten percent of contract price, whether the drawing, design and specifications of construction work requires to be changed or not, by the chief of the Public Entity of the gazetted second class, by assigning technical justification, after obtaining the approval of one level higher authority, and variation order of up to fifteen percent by the Departmental chief by assigning technical justification,
- The Sub clause (2) - clause 118 of the Public Procurement Act 2063 (2006) further states that if

a variation order exceeding fifteen percent of the contract price requires to be issued, a proposal shall be submitted on the recommendation of a committee consisting of chief of the financial administration section, chief of the concerned Department and one officer or expert concerned with this matter designated by the secretary under the chairpersonship of the concerned secretary in the case of the Public Entity under sub-clause (1) of clause (b) of Section 2 of the Act to the Government of Nepal, Council of Ministers and in the case of other Public Entity to the supreme executive body of that entity.

It further states that no variation order shall be issued with a rate exceeding the rate referred to in the procurement contract. If a variation order requires to be issued in excess of the rate, an approval shall be obtained from one level higher authority after making the rate analysis as well.

If a new item requires to be added to the construction works under the procurement contract, the Public Entity shall have to determine the rate by analyzing the rate as well of such a new item.

As per Public Procurement Act 2063 (First revision 2073) and Public Procurement regulation 2064 (third revision 2073), variation order can be issued by the procurement entity as follow:

- VO upto 5% is entitled to be approved by gazetted second class officer or equivalent chief of public entity.
- If the procurement entity is led by the gazetted first

class officer she/he is entitled to approve the variations upto 10% of the contract price.

- VO upto 15% is to be approved by Department Chief.
- VO greater than 25% should be submitted to the council of the ministers for approval.

The provision also says that no extra work should be carried out without formal approval of the VO and no VO should be approved without duly provisioning the budget required for it. Any VO cannot be approved by an officer of lower rank than the one who approved the estimate. The procedure for VO approval is well described in the act and regulation. VO should not mean to change the scope and design of the project.

Methodology

Since the study is extension of Mishra and Bhandari(2018) on Performance Assessment of ongoing Construction projects under Town Development Fund, Nepal published in International Journal of Advanced Research in Civil & Structural Engineering volume 1, Issue 2, Methodology is adopted from the same.

The convenient sampling has been done in this study. The sampling has been done in such a way to include the respondents from each project.

Among total respondents, this study enrolled more than two third of the respondents as contractor, about one fifth of the respondents were client and rest of the others were consultant.

Table 1. Respondents Status

Projects	Respondents (Client)		Respondents (Consultant)		Respondents (Contractor)	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Pokhara Shopping Complex at Srijana Chowk	1	6.25%	2	16.67%	6	11.11%
Office cum Shopping Complex-Byas Municipality	2	12.50%	2	16.67%	6	11.11%
Birgunj Bus Park	1	6.25%	1	8.33%	5	9.26%
Birendranagar Bus Park	1	6.25%	1	8.33%	5	9.26%
Reinstatement of Municipal building	2	12.50%	1	8.33%	5	9.26%
Bheemdatt Bus Park	2	12.50%	1	8.33%	6	11.11%
Biratnagar Bus Terminal	2	12.50%	1	8.33%	6	11.11%
Nepalgunj Bus Park	2	12.50%	1	8.33%	5	9.26%
Improvement of meena bazar and drainage-	2	12.50%	1	8.33%	5	9.26%
Butwal Bus Terminal	1	6.25%	1	8.33%	5	9.26%
Sub Total	16	100.00%	12	100.00%	54	100.00%
Grand Total	82					

The five-point scale ranged from 1 (not important) to 5 (extremely important) was adopted and transformed to relative importance indices (RII) for each factor. Relative importance index in this study had been computed by opting the formula for relative importance index. The total scores of weighting given to each factor by the respondents were summed up and divided by the multiplication of total sample and highest weighting for each factor. The mathematical expression for RII is provided by:

$$RII = \frac{1x(n1) + 2x(n2) + 3x(n3) + 4x(n3) + 5x(n3)}{5 \times (n1+n2+n3+n4+n5)}$$

The computed relative importance for each factors were arranged in descending order i.e. highest value being in a first or top column followed by the lower ones. Thus, the rank was obtained for each factor. Similar process for calculation of relative importance index was computed for perceived effects too.

Factors affecting the performance

The perceived view of the personnel from Client, the Consultant and the Contractor has been presented and discussed in the subsequent sections.

Client related factors

The perceived view of the respondents for the client related factors is listed in table 4-3 below:

• Clients' Perception

For finance and payment of completed work on client related factors, it was found that about 80 % of the Clients' personnel responded this as the considerably important issue and remaining 20% responded it as less important factor. Also, owner interference on client related factors was pointed out to be very important by 45% while 54% of those surveyed stating it important at all. Slow decision making was seen very important overall on client related factors. Likewise, unrealistic contract duration and requirements imposed over client related factors were considered less important or no important with 20% of those surveyed believing on this fact while rest 80% of those surveyed marking the fact less important or important only.

• Consultants' Perception

For finance and payment of completed work on client related factors, it was found that about 92 % of the Clients' personnel responded this as the considerably important issue and remaining 8% responded it as less important factor. Also, owner interference on client related factors was pointed out to be very important by 42% while 33% of those surveyed stating it important and 25% states it as less or not important. Slow decision making was been pointed out as very important issue by 67% while 33% considered this as important issues. None of the respondents pointed out it as less important issue. Likewise, unrealistic contract

Table 2. Client Related Factors

CLR:: Clients' Representative; CSR: Consultants' Representative; CNR: Contractors' Representative													
CLR		Finance and payment of completed work			Owner interference			Slow decision making			Unrealistic contract duration and requirements imposed		
		CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR
Not Important	Nos	-	-	-	-	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	1
	%	-	-	-	-	16.66	3.70	-	-	-	-	-	1.85
Less Important	Nos	1	1	6	5	1	5	-	-	-	3	1	2
	%	6.25	8.33	11.11	31.25	8.33	9.26	-	-	-	18.75	8.33	3.70
Important	Nos	2	1	21	4	4	30	9	4	20	8	6	18
	%	12.50	8.33	38.39	25.00	33.33	55.56	56.25	33.33	37.40	50.00	50.00	33.33
Very Important	Nos	12	10	22	3	5	11	7	7	32	5	5	31
	%	75.00	83.33	40.74	18.75	41.67	20.37	43.75	58.33	59.26	31.25	41.67	57.41
Extremely Important	Nos	1	-	5	4	-	6	-	1	2	-	-	2
	%	6.25	-	9.26	25.00	-	11.11	-	8.33	3.70	-	-	3.70
Total	Nos	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54
	%	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

duration and requirements imposed over client related factors were considered less important or no important by 10% of those surveyed while 90% of those surveyed marking the fact as considerably important issue.

- **Contractors' Perception**

For finance and payment of completed work on client related factors, it was found that about 50% of the Clients' personnel responded this as the considerably important issue, 39% considered this as important issue and remaining 11% responded it as less important factor. Owner interference on client related factors was pointed out to be substantial important by 31% while 56% of those surveyed stating it important and 13% states it as less or not important. Slow decision making was been pointed out as very important issue by 63% while 37% considered this as important issues. None of the respondents pointed out it as less important issue. Likewise, unrealistic contract duration and requirements imposed over client related factors were considered less important or no important by 5% of those surveyed while 95% of those surveyed marking the fact as considerably important issue.

- **Observation**

From the table, mixed reaction from all concerned parties has been obtained. All Parties considered finance and Payment of related work as a major issues. Owner Interference is also considered as an important issue by all concerned. Same is the case with slow decision making and unrealistic Contract duration also. It is to be noted here that even Clients' representative also accepts the issues from the Client side were vital factors that affects the performance of the project.

Contractor related Factors

The perceived view of the respondents for the contractor related factor is listed in table 4-4 below.

- **Clients' Perception**

As far as contractor related factors is concerned, subcontractors issues were considered as substantially important factor affecting the performance of the project, though 25% of the respondents also considered this as not so important issue. All respondents considered issues related to the site management as one of the crucial issue. Same is the case with appropriate Construction Methods and preparation and approval of drawing as well. Quality assurance is not considered as an extremely important issue, however, all respondents agreed that QA is one of the important issue that affects the performance.

- **Consultants' Perception**

As far as contractor related factors is concerned,

subcontractors were considered as substantially important factor by about three-fourth of those surveyed. Site management by the contractor is considered to be important by 93% of the consultant representatives. Construction methods were marked important by 58% of the respondents while 17% mentioned it as important factor and remaining respondent marked it as less important factor. Preparation and approval of drawings was seen as substantially important by 50% of the respondents. 50% respondents believed quality assurance substantially important factors. On the other hand, 42% of the respondents considered waiting time for approval of tests as very important factor while 50% considered this as an important factor and remaining 8% considered this as less important factor.

- **Contractors' Perception**

Contractors' representative considered subcontractors related issues to be substantially important factor by 65% of those surveyed. Site management by the contractor is considered to be important by 93% of the contractors' representatives. Construction methods were marked important by 61% of the respondents while 13% mentioned it as important factor and remaining respondent marked it as less or not important factor. Preparation and approval of drawings was seen as substantially important by 80% of the respondents. 85% respondents believed quality assurance substantially important factors. On the other hand, 47% of the respondents considered waiting time for approval of tests as very important factor while 6% considered this as an important factor and remaining 47% considered this as less important factor.

- **Observation**

It is observed that the perception on the factors affecting the performance is more or less same for most of the respondents irrespective their position and belongings. It can be evidenced by the fact that most of the respondents from all three parties considered Sub Contractors related issues as "important to very important issue". Same is the case for Site Management, Construction methods, preparation and approval of drawings, Quality assurance and waiting time for approval of tests as well.

Consultant Related Factors

The perceived view of the respondents for the consultant related factors are listed in table 4-5 below.

- **Clients' Perception**

With respect to the consultant related factor, 18% of those surveyed related contract management as an important issue while 80% relating contract management as very important to extremely important issue. Similarly,

Table 3. Contractor Related Factors

CLR:: Clients' Representative; CSR: Consultants' Representative; CNR: Contractors' Representative																			
CLR		Sub contractors			Site management			Construction methods			Preparation and approval of drawings			Quality assurance			Waiting time for approval of tests		
		CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	
Not Important	Nos	3	2	12	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	2	-	-	10
	%	18.75	16.67	22.22	-	-	-	-	-	1.85	-	-	1.85	-	-	3.70	-	-	18.52
Less Important	Nos	1	1	7	-	1	4	-	3	13	-	-	1	3	1	6	3	7	15
	%	6.25	8.33	12.96	-	8.33	7.41	-	25.00	24.07	-	-	1.85	18.75	8.33	11.11	18.75	58.33	27.78
Important	Nos	6	5	25	3	4	23	9	2	7	7	6	9	8	6	14	8	-	3
	%	37.50	41.67	46.30	18.75	33.33	42.59	56.25	16.67	12.96	43.75	50.00	16.67	50.00	50.00	25.93	50.00	-	5.56
Very Important	Nos	5	4	4	10	7	27	7	6	13	9	1	2	5	5	24	5	5	5
	%	31.25	33.33	7.41	62.50	58.33	50.00	43.75	50.00	24.07	56.25	8.33	3.70	31.25	41.67	44.44	31.25	41.67	9.26
Extremely Important	Nos	1	-	6	3	-	-	-	1	20	-	5	41	-	-	8	-	-	21
	%	6.25	-	11.11	18.75	-	-	-	8.33	37.04	-	41.67	75.93	-	-	14.81	-	-	38.89
Total	Nos	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54
	%	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Table 4. Consultant Related Factors

CLR:: Clients' Representative; CSR: Consultants' Representative; CNR: Contractors' Representative													
CLR		Contract Management			Preparation and Approval of Drawing			Quality assurance			Waiting time for approval of tests and inspections		
		CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	
Not Important	Nos	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	5
	%	-	-	1.85	-	-	-	-	-	1.85	6.25	-	9.26
Less Important	Nos	1	1	15	2	1	5	-	-	10	4	1	19
	%	6.25	8.33	27.78	12.50	8.33	9.26	-	-	18.52	25.00	8.33	35.19
Important	Nos	2	1	12	2	2	14	9	4	9	5	6	4
	%	12.50	8.33	22.22	12.50	16.67	25.93	56.25	33.33	16.67	31.25	50.00	7.41
Very Important	Nos	12	10	26	1	1	7	7	7	14	2	5	1
	%	75.00	83.33	48.15	6.25	8.33	12.96	43.75	58.33	25.93	12.50	41.67	1.85
Extremely Important	Nos	1	-	-	11	8	28	-	1	20	4	-	25
	%	6.25	-	-	68.75	66.67	51.85	-	8.33	37.04	25.00	-	46.30
Total	Nos	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54
	%	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Preparation and approval of drawing was seen as an important to less important issue by 25% of the respondents and 75% respondents marking the issue as very important to extremely important. Also, quality assurance was seen important to very important in the view of all of the respondents. 31% of the respondents considered waiting time for approval of tests and inspections as less important factor for the consultant related factors while 31% considering waiting time for approval of tests and inspections important and 25 % considering it extremely important for the consultant related factors.

• Consultants' Perception

83% of those surveyed related contract management as very important issue, 8 % relating contract management as important and remaining respondents considered this as less important issue. Preparation and approval of drawing was seen as an extremely important issue by 67% of the respondents, 8% respondents marking the issue as very important issue and remaining 25% considered this as important to less important issue. Also, quality assurance was seen important to extremely important issue by 8% and very important by 58% while 33% of those surveyed considered this as important issue. 42% of the respondents considered waiting time for approval of tests and inspections as very important factor for the consultant related factor while 50% considering waiting

time for approval of tests and inspections important and 8 % considering it extremely important for the consultant related factors.

• Contractors' Perception

48% of those surveyed related contract management as very important issue, 22 % relating contract management as important and remaining respondents considered this as less important issue. Preparation and approval of drawing was seen as an extremely important issue by 52% of the respondents, 13% respondents marking the issue as very important issue and remaining 36% considered this as important to less important issue. Also, quality assurance was seen important to extremely important issue by 37% and very important by 58% while 33% of those surveyed considered this as important issue. 48% of the respondents considered waiting time for approval of tests and inspections as very important factor for the consultant related factor while 7% considering waiting time for approval of tests and inspections important and 45 % considering it less or not important for the consultant related factors.

• Observation

Issues generated due to preparation and approval of drawings are considered to be extremely important by most of the respondents of all parties while the issues that are

used to be generated were considered as very important by the most of the respondents. Quality Assurance is also considered as very important by 45% of the Clients representative, 60% of the Consultants’ representative and only 26% of the Clients’ representative. It seems that the Consultant are more concerned on the quality related issues while the Contractors seems to provide less priority on these issues.

Material related factors:

The perceived view of the respondents for the Material related factors is listed in table 4-6.

Contractors’ Perception

Similar to Clients’ representative and Consultants’ representative, greater emphasis was given to the quality of the material resulting 92% of those surveyed relying upon its importance in material related factor. In the same way, 87% of those surveyed agreed upon the fact that shortage of material was the major reason behind material related factor.

Observation

Almost 80% of those surveyed pointed out issue related

Table 5. Material Related Factors

CLR: Clients’ Representative; CSR: Consultants’ Representative; CNR: Contractors’ Representative										
CLR		Labour Supply			Labour Productivity			Equipment availability and failure		
		CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	
Not Important	Nos	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	4
	%	-	-	-	-	-	1.85	-	-	7.41
Less Important	Nos	1	1	2	2	1	5	9	5	10
	%	6.25	8.33	3.70	12.50	8.33	9.26	56.25	41.67	18.52
Important	Nos	2	1	22	2	8	43	7	3	3
	%	12.50	8.33	40.74	12.50	66.67	79.63	73.75	25.00	5.56
Very Important	Nos	13	10	30	12	3	5	-	3	29
	%	81.25	83.33	55.56	75.00	25.00	9.26	-	25.00	53.70
Extremely Important	Nos	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	8
	%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.33	14.81
Total	Nos	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54
	%	100	100	100	100	100	100	130	100	100

Clients’ Perception

With respect to the material related factor, greater emphasis was given to the quality of the material resulting 81% of those surveyed relying upon its importance in material related factors. In the same way, 69% of those surveyed agreed upon the fact that shortage of material was the major reason behind material related factor.

Consultants’ Perception

83% of those surveyed had given greater emphasis to the quality of the material and 67% of those surveyed agreed upon the fact that shortage of material was the major reason behind material related factor.

to quality of material as very important issue. Similarly around 60% of Clients representative and Consultants’ representative considered shortage of material as an extremely important issue while only 26% of Contractor’s representative considered this as an extremely important issue.

Labour and Equipment related factors

The perceived view of the respondents for Labour and Equipment related factors is listed in table 4-7 below.

Clients’ Perception

Focusing on the labour and equipment category factors, it was seen that labour supply is an important factor

for construction delay with 94% respondents agreeing on this. Likewise, labour productivity was seen equally important with 87% respondents agreeing and merely 13% respondents disagreeing and thus making it less important on labour and equipment category factors. Finally concerning equipment availability and failure upon labour and equipment category factors, it is concluded that 44% of the respondents believe this to be important against the rest 56% respondents believing the same as less important issue.

Contractors' representative considered labour supply issue as very important issue. In case of labour supply, 75% of the respondents from the client side considered it as very important issue while only 25% of the Consultant's representative and 9% of the Contractors' representative considered it as very important issue. Contractors seem little bit more sensitive on Equipment availability and failure as 70% of those surveyed considered issue related to equipment availability as extremely important to very important.

Table 6. labour and equipment category factors

CLR: Clients' Representative; CSR: Consultants' Representative; CNR: Contractors' Representative										
CLR		Labour Supply			Labour Productivity			Equipment availability and failure		
		CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	
Not Important	Nos	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	4
	%	-	-	-	-	-	1.85	-	-	7.41
Less Important	Nos	1	1	2	2	1	5	9	5	10
	%	6.25	8.33	3.70	12.50	8.33	9.26	56.25	41.67	18.52
Important	Nos	2	1	22	2	8	43	7	3	3
	%	12.50	8.33	40.74	12.50	66.67	79.63	73.75	25.00	5.56
Very Important	Nos	13	10	30	12	3	5	-	3	29
	%	81.25	83.33	55.56	75.00	25.00	9.26	-	25.00	53.70
Extremely Important	Nos	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	8
	%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.33	14.81
Total	Nos	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54
	%	100	100	100	100	100	100	130	100	100

• Consultants' Perception

Labour supply has been seen very important factor with 83% respondents agreeing on this. Likewise, labour productivity was seen equally important with 92% respondents agreeing and merely 8% respondents disagreeing and thus making it less important on labour and equipment category factors. Finally concerning equipment availability and failure upon labour and equipment category factors, it is concluded that 58% of the respondents believe this to be important against the rest 42% respondents believing the same as less important issue.

• Observation

Almost 90% of the respondents from Client and Consultants and Contractors considered Labour supply issue as important to very important issue while 56% of

Contract Related Factors

The perceived view of the respondents for the Contract related factors is listed in table 4-8.

• Clients' Perception

With respect to the change in orders upon contract related factors, it can be inferred that more than half i.e.43.7% of those surveyed believe that it is less important while the remaining 56.3% of those surveyed believing the issue of change in orders as important factor in contract related factor. Similarly, mistakes and discrepancies in contract documents was considered as the very important factor with 43.75% of those surveyed marking this issue as prime factor in contract related factors while 56.25% marked this as important to less important issues.

Table 7.Contract Related Factors

CLR		Change orders			Mistakes and discrepancies in contract documents		
		CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	
Not Important	Nos	-	-	-	-	-	1
	%	-	-	-	-	-	1.85
Less Important	Nos	7	6	31	2	1	4
	%	43.75	50.00	57.41	12.50	8.33	7.41
Important	Nos	2	1	8	7	4	20
	%	12.50	8.33	14.81	43.75	33.33	37.04
Very Important	Nos	3	3	6	7	5	28
	%	18.75	25.00	11.11	43.75	41.67	51.85
Extremely Important	Nos	4	2	9	-	2	1
	%	25.00	16.67	16.67	-	16.67	1.85
Total	Nos	16	12	54	16	12	54
	%	100	100	100	100	100	100

• Consultants’ Perception

About half of those surveyed believe that change in orders as less important, 8% considered this as important issues while the remaining 42% of those surveyed believing the issue of change in orders as considerably important factor in contract related factor. Similarly, mistakes and discrepancies in contract documents was considered as the very important factor with 58% of those surveyed marking this issue as prime factor in contract related factors while 42% marked this as important to less important issues.

• Contractors’ Perception

far as change orders upon contract related factors, it can be inferred that more than half of those surveyed believe that it is less important, 15% considered this as important issues while the remaining 28% of those surveyed believing the issue of change in orders as considerably important factor in contract related factor. Similarly, mistakes and discrepancies in contract documents was considered as the very important factor with 54% of those surveyed marking this issue as prime factor in contract related factors while 46% marked this as important to less important issues.

Observation

In this particular case also, it seems that the respondents from all parties have more or less same view. Change orders issues were considered less important by almost 50% of the

respondents from each party while 19%, 25% and 11% from Client, Consultant and Contractor respectively considered it as very important issue. In the same way, around 45% on average considered issue related to materials and discrepancies as very important issue.

Contract relationship related factors

The perceived view of the respondents for the Contract relationship related factors is listed in table 4-9 below.

Clients’ Perception

Looking after the major disputes and negotiations on contract relationship related factor, 63.5% of the respondents mark this issue as the significantly important factor. However, remaining 37.5% of the respondents mark this as the less important issue on contract relationship related factors. Also, inappropriate overall organization structure linking to the project was seen as the very important factor with 75% of the respondents agreeing on this and only 25 % of the respondents marking this factor as important to less important on the contract relationship related factor. Similarly, the hindrance caused by lack of communication between the parties was also realized to be one of the most important factors by 6% of the respondents on the contract relationship related factors. 94% of the respondents believed that lack of communication between the parties to be less important on the contract relationship related factor.

Table 8.Contract relationship related factors

CLR: Clients' Representative; CSR: Consultants' Representative; CNR: Contractors' Representative										
CLR		Major disputes and negotiation			Inappropriate overall Organizational structure Linking to the project			Lack of communication between parties		
		CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	
Not Important	Nos	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
	%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.70
Less Important	Nos	4	3	12	2	1	11	-	1	7
	%	25.00	25.00	22.22	12.50	8.33	20.37	-	8.33	12.96
Important	Nos	6	7	35	2	5	19	10	8	37
	%	37.50	58.33	64.81	12.50	41.67	35.19	62.50	66.67	68.52
Very Important	Nos	2	2	2	12	6	24	5	2	6
	%	12.50	16.67	3.70	75.00	50.00	44.44	31.25	16.67	11.11
Extremely Important	Nos	4	-	5	-	-	-	1	1	2
	%	25.00	-	9.26	-	-	-	6.25	8.33	3.70
Total	Nos	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54
	%	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

• Consultants' Perception

17% of the respondents mark major disputes and negotiations on contract relationship related factor as the significantly important factor, 58% of the respondents mark this as the important issue on contract relationship related factor. Also, inappropriate overall organization structure linking to the project was seen as the very important factor with 50% of the respondents agreeing on this and only 8 % of the respondents marking this factor as less important on the contract relationship related factors. Similarly, the hindrance caused by lack of communication between the parties was also realized to be one of the most important factors by 25% of the respondents on the contract relationship related factor. 75% of the respondents believed that lack of communication between the parties to be less important on the contract relationship related factor.

• Contractors' Perception

It has been observed that major disputes and negotiations on contract relationship related factor, 13% of the respondents mark this issue as the significantly important factors, 87% of the respondents mark this as the important issue on contract relationship related factor. Also, inappropriate overall organization structure linking to the project was seen as the very important factor with 44% of the respondents agreeing on this and only 20 % of the respondents marking

this factor as less important on the contract relationship related factor. Similarly, the hindrance caused by lack of communication between the parties was also realized to be one of the most important factors by 15% of the respondents on the contract relationship related factor. 69% of the respondents believed that lack of communication between the parties to be important and 17% respondents considered this issue as Less or not important issue.

• Observation

More weightage was given for the issue generated by the Major disputes and Clients followed by the Contractor and Consultant. Similarly issues generated by lack of communication between parties and inappropriate overall organisation structure, more weightage were given by the client followed by the consultant and the contractor.

External Factors

The perceived view of the respondents for the External factors is listed in table 4-10 below.

• Clients' Perception

As far as the external factors are concerned, 19% of the respondents responded weather conditions as one of the major factor behind construction delay. However, 31% and 44% of the respondents mark weather conditions as

important and less important respectively. Mixed responses were found when asked about the importance of regulatory charges. About half of the respondents i.e. 44% believed regulatory charges as an important issue on the external factors whereas approximately the other half i.e. 56% of the respondents believe regulatory charges as less or not important issue on external factors. Nearly three-fourth of the respondents i.e. 75% take the issue of problem with neighbours as significantly important while the remaining one-fourth i.e. 25% of the respondents mark the issue of problem with neighbours as extremely important. Unforeseen site condition was marked considerably important by more than half of the respondents i.e. 69% whereas the remaining 31% of the respondents marking the issue less important upon the subject of external factors.

believe regulatory charges as less or not important issue on external factors. Nearly three-fourth of the respondents i.e. 50% and 25% take the issue of problem with neighbours as less important and important issues respectively, while the remaining one-fourth i.e. 25% of the respondents mark the issue of problem with neighbours as very important. Unforeseen site condition was marked considerably important by 25% of the respondents, 25% of them considered as important issues whereas the remaining 50% of the respondents marking the issue less important upon the subject of external factors.

Contractors' Perception

17% of the respondents responded weather conditions as

Table 9.External Factors

CLR: Clients' Representative; CSR: Consultants' Representative; CNR: Contractors' Representative													
CLR		Weather conditions			Regulatory changes			Problem with neighbors			Unforeseen site conditions		
		CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR	CSR	CNR	CLR
Not Important	Nos	1	-	7	4	1	7	-	-	2	-	-	2
	%	6.25	-	12.96	25.00	8.33	12.96	-	-	3.70	-	-	3.70
Less Important	Nos	7	5	21	5	6	21	3	2	14	5	6	22
	%	43.75	41.67	38.89	31.25	50.00	38.89	18.75	16.67	25.93	31.25	50.00	40.74
Important	Nos	5	4	17	5	2	17	9	7	30	3	3	11
	%	31.25	33.33	31.48	31.25	16.67	31.48	56.25	58.33	55.56	18.75	25.00	20.37
Very Important	Nos	2	2	9	2	3	9	-	1	3	8	3	18
	%	12.50	16.67	16.67	12.50	25.00	16.67	-	8.33	5.56	50.00	25.00	33.33
Extremely Important	Nos	1	1	-	-	-	-	4	2	5	-	-	1
	%	6.25	8.33	-	-	-	-	25.00	16.67	9.26	-	-	1.85
Total	Nos	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54	16	12	54
	%	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Consultants' Perception

Only 25% of the respondents responded weather conditions as one of the major factors behind construction delay. However, 33% and 42% of the respondents mark weather conditions as important and less important respectively. Mixed responses were found when asked about the importance of regulatory charges. About half of the respondents i.e. 42% believed regulatory charges as an important issue on the external factors whereas approximately the other half i.e. 58% of the respondents

one of the major factor behind construction delay. However, 39% and 32% of the respondents mark weather conditions as important and less important respectively. Mixed responses were found when asked about the importance of regulatory charges. About half of the respondents i.e. 49% believed regulatory charges as an important issue on the external factors whereas approximately the other half i.e. 51% of the respondents believe regulatory charges as less or not important issue on external factors. Nearly three-fourth of the respondents i.e. 26% and 56% take the issue of problem with neighbours as less important

and important issues respectively, while the remaining respondents mark the issue of problem with neighbours as very important. Unforeseen site condition was marked considerably important by 35% of the respondents, 21% of them considered as important issues whereas the remaining 41% of the respondents marking the issue less important upon the subject of external factors.

• Observation

Similarity to some extent is observed in this section also between all concerned parties. Weather condition was considered as less important issue by around 40% of the respondents from client, Consultant and Contractors while around 30% considered this as an important issue. Issues due to change in regulatory system has been marked as less important by 50% of the Contractors' representative while around 35% respondents from client and Consultants' representative marked this as less important. Issues generated due to problems with neighbours were marked as important issue hindering the project performance by about 55% of the respondents from all concerned Parties. Unforeseen site condition were observed as less important issue by 50% of the respondents from the consultant while 30% and 40% from Client and Contractor respectively has marked this issue as less important.

As a whole, there were mixed perceptions observed among the respondents from Client, Consultants and the Contractors for the factor affecting the performance of the Project. However, in most of the cases, the perception of each parties resembles with each other. No drastic or sharp difference in perception of all concerned parties has been observed. In my opinion, this is because all parties mentioned in this study (Client, Consultant and Contractors) are involved in same projects though in different role. They may have encountered same problems which are affecting the project performance in general.

Level of Importance for the factors affecting performance of projects

In addition, the ranking of those factors has also been done so as to have clearer idea of the factors that are affecting most in the smooth operation of the projects. Ranking of the factors has been done using relative importance index method.

This study computed the rank of each factors according to relative importance index. Relative importance index in this particular study has been computed by opting the formula for relative importance index. The total scores of weighting given to each factor by the respondents were summed up and divided by the multiplication of total sample and highest weighting for each factor. The computed relative importance for each factors were arranged in descending order i.e. highest value being in a first or top

column followed by the lower ones. Thus, the rank was obtained for each factor. Similar results were found in case of hydropower projects of Nepal by Chiluwal and Mishra, (2017) and Chuluwal and Mishra, (2018).

Table 10. Ranking of the factors affecting the project performance according to relative importance index

Factors affecting the Performance	RII	Rank
Preparation and approval of drawings (contractor related) after joint survey submittal	0.8361	1
Preparation & approval of drawings (consultant related initial drawings)	0.8217	2
Shortage in material	0.7880	3
Quality Assurance	0.7325	4
Quality of material	0.7229	5
Slow decision making	0.7181	6
Construction methods	0.7133	7
Labour supply	0.7108	8
Finance and payments of completed work	0.7084	9
Site management	0.7012	10
Unrealistic contract duration and requirements imposed	0.6819	11
Mistakes and discrepancies in contract documents	0.6819	12
Quality assurance/control	0.6795	13
Equipment availability and failure	0.6747	14
Contract Management	0.6675	15
Waiting Time for approval of tests & inspections	0.6651	16
Inappropriate overall organizational structure liking to the project	0.6602	17
Owner interference	0.6410	18
Waiting time for approval of tests and inspection	0.6217	19
Labour productivity	0.6169	20
Lack of communication between the parties	0.6145	21
Major disputes and negotiations	0.6048	22
Problem with neighbours	0.6000	23
Change orders	0.5880	24
Unforeseen site condition	0.5783	25
Weather condition	0.5566	26
Subcontractors	0.5542	27
Regulatory changes	0.4916	28

The table 4-11 showed that preparation and approval of drawings that is related to contractor was rank one factor of delays in construction projects followed by the same factor related to consultant being the second one. In fact, this ranking indicates that the contractors, in general, have to change their traditional working style. The technical experts needs to be hired and should be given privilege so as to improve the documentation quality and thereby enhancing the capability to prepare technical drawings. On the other hand consultant should also have to provide their consent as quickly as possible for “go-ahead” once the finalisation of the design and drawings. Unusual extended time must not be spent to check or rectify the design and drawings. Shortage of material is on the third ranking in this study. The findings of this study were quite comparable to the findings of the study done in Malaysian construction industry. Sambasivan and Soon (2007) found out material related factor to be one of the most important factors among the other groups for the delays in construction projects since the value of relative importance index is highest in material related factor followed by other factors. This fact indeed holds true for the construction projects as the short of materials would always have much attribution for delays in construction despite having good planning and coordination ensured. In addition, all projects under consideration have been passed through the harsh situation of devastating Earthquake and the blockade by agitated political parties in the border. So shortage of material is obviously highest among the other issues that have hindered the project performance.

Quality Assurance and Quality of material falls under fourth and fifth ranking in this research. Most probably, low bidding is the prime factor for deteriorating the quality of the material and end products. This problem needs to be addressed from high level policy makers of the nation. Slow decision making falls under 6th place during ranking. All the projects under study are executed by the public sector and we are well aware that decision making in public sector are not as easy as in private sector. Construction methods also are a vital factor that is needed to be considered and in this study it is ranked in seventh position. Poor construction methodologies are also the result of low bidding. The competency and goodwill of the contractor, therefore, has to be accessed before bidding.

Labour supply is in the 8th rank in this study. In fact, I am surprised to see it in 8th position! In fact brain drain is the main problem of our nation. Most of the young generation were either ‘vanished’ or settled in other countries in absence of social security’s and bottom line facilities. In such context, it is not astonishing that the unavailability of the labour is also one of the major factors affecting the performance of the project. Similarly Payment related problem is in 9th position of this ranking.

Site Management Issue comes under 10th Category in this study. It is obvious that site management is the sole responsibility of the Contractor. Clients are just the facilitator to liaise with the line agencies. Again here comes the issue of low bidding! The low bidding, obviously done by less competent contractor, can’t afford qualified personnel and hence site management can’t be done properly. Unrealistic contract duration falls under 11th position during ranking. It indicates that the duration shall be provided to the contract considering the various outside factors like bandh, riots, commotion etc. The ideal or theoretical time provided may be insufficient to the contractor to execute the work under scope properly. Mistakes discrepancies in contract documents have fallen under 12th ranking. The discrepancies in the document are in fact a serious issue. The incapable people preparing the contract document and the inappropriate and the inefficient people filling the contract document duly has generally caused this factor as one of the issue hindering the project performance. Particularly, in this study, as the projects under consideration are small in magnitude, the Mistakes and discrepancies in contract documents has fallen on least position in ranking.

Quality Control is in 13th ranking followed by the equipment availability and failure which is in 14th rank. The equipment and machineries are, no doubt, very important aspect for the execution of work. Contract Management has been ranked in 15th position in this research. Waiting Time for approval of tests & inspections is in 16th position with relative importance index of 0.6651. Inappropriate overall organizational structure and owner interference fall under 17th and 18th ranking respectively. Waiting time for approval of tests and inspection and Labour productivity has been ranked in 19th and 20th position respectively.

In this ranking regulatory changes has been ranked in 28th position (i.e., in last position). Obviously, the regulatory changes occur rarely.

In all, the factors listed in table 4-11 are likely to occur either in isolation or concurrently with each other causing concurrent delay. Concurrent delay is the delay caused by more than one factor simultaneously with one or more cause being driving factors. Concurrent delay may be caused by more than one stakeholder simultaneously. The best example is, for instance, the client is not able to hand over the access to site and at the same time, the contractor is also not able to mobilise his resources properly.

Quality Control is in 13th ranking followed by the equipment availability and failure which is in 14th rank. The equipment and machineries are, no doubt, very important aspect for the execution of work. Contract Management has been ranked in 15th position in this research. Waiting Time for approval of tests & inspections is in 16th position with

relative importance index of 0.6651. Inappropriate overall organizational structure and owner interference fall under 17th and 18th ranking respectively. Waiting time for approval of tests and inspection and Labour productivity has been ranked in 19th and 20th position respectively.

In this ranking regulatory changes has been ranked in 28th position (i.e., in last position). Obviously, the regulatory changes occur rarely.

Table 11. Level of Importance according to the group

Factors affecting the project performance in Construction Project a/c to groups	RII	Rank
Material related factors	0.7554	1
Consultant related factors	0.7217	2
Client related factors	0.6873	3
Contractor related factors	0.6840	4
Labour and equipment category factors	0.6675	5
Contract related factors	0.6349	6
Contract relationship related factors	0.6265	7
External factors	0.5566	8

Table 4-12 showed the ranking of factors affecting project performance according to the category listed in the questionnaire. The relative importance score for individual factor was grouped according to the questionnaire and average RII was computed for each groups. The analysis yielded the rank for each group the first being the material related factors for the delays in construction project. Similarly, this study revealed the consultant related factors to be the second followed by client related factor, contractor related factors and so on, the least important factor being the external factor.

Perceived effects of factors affecting the performance

As Consequences of the factors listed in section 4.2, the ongoing projects have affected the projects adversely. The perceived effects were ranked in the table 4-13:

Cost overrun was seen as much more important issue with majority of those surveyed i.e. 98.8% pointing the issue significantly important. Arbitration was also seen as an important issue with 90.3% of those surveyed believing that it has a considerable effect on projects and 9.8% of

those surveyed thought of arbitration as less important issue on effects on projects. About little more than half i.e. 57.4% of those surveyed thought of litigation as less important factor affecting the project. On the other hand, 29.3% and 13.4% of those surveyed believed litigation as very important and important issue respectively. The opinion upon dispute arousal had more respondents i.e. 59.7% agree upon its less significance while the remaining 40.3 % respondents agree upon its significance in factors affecting the project. Finally, the total abandonment had 52.4% of those surveyed agree upon its importance and 12.2% of those surveyed agree upon its further more importance. However, 20.7% of those surveyed agree upon the statement that total abandonment has no any effect on projects with 14.6% of those surveyed focusing upon its less importance in effects on projects.

Table 12. Effects of performance factors

	Cost over run	Arbitration	Litigation	Dispute arousal	Total abandonment
Not Important	-	-	3 (3.7)	2 (2.4)	17 (20.7)
Less Important	1 (1.2)	8 (9.8)	44 (53.7)	47 (57.3)	12 (14.6)
Important	34 (41.5)	59 (72)	11 (13.4)	29 (35.4)	43 (52.4)
Very Important	24 (29.3)	15 (18.3)	24 (29.3)	4 (4.9)	10 (12.2)
Extremely Important	23 (28.0)	-	-	-	-
Total	82 (100)	82 (100)	82 (100)	82 (100)	82 (100)

Table 13. Ranking of effects according to relative importance index

Effects	RII	Rank
Cost Overrun	0.759036	1
Arbitration (Negotiation)	0.609639	2
Litigation	0.53012	3
Dispute Arousal	0.506024	4
Total abandonment	0.479518	5

This study also had questions on the perceptions of the respondents on probable effects of delays in construction

projects; similar procedure was opted to rank the effects as done prior to rank factor of delays. The highest value of RII attached with the effect variables were arranged in descending order. Doing so, this study showed that cost overrun being one of the most important effects of delays in construction project followed by arbitration, litigation, dispute arousal and last being the total abandonment of the project.

This study revealed that there were respondents who were between the age of 20 years and 59 years. Majority were between the ages less than 29 years, the least being the age of more than 50 years. Regarding education of the respondents, majority were graduates and almost 80 % were found to be graduates or above and is quite expected that the human resources working in a construction projects have higher educational level with greater cognition and glib skills. The findings of this study were quite comparable to the findings of the study done in Malaysian construction industry. Similarly, there were minorities forming the consultants being only 19.5 % and around two third being contractors. Similarly very few responded that they were non executives followed by the respondents working in managerial level & more than two third working in an executive level. More than two third of the respondents had experiences between 2 to 10 years followed by more than 10 years who were 28% , only 1 responded that he/she had less than a year of experience. Moreover, more than two third of the respondents were experienced in the field of infrastructure and remaining were experienced on building. The second important factor being the consultant related factor followed by client related factor and contractor related factor and so on in study. The findings of this study is somewhat comparable to study done in Malaysia where top ranked factor was identified as contractor related factor and second being material related factor and so on (Sambasivan and Soon, 2007). Conversely, the study done in Jordan has different rankings as compared to this study where the top ranked factor for delays was identified as client related factor which is both responded by consultants and contractors. Similarly, the priorities for factor were different for consultants and contractors in the study done in Jordan (Odeh and Battaineh, 2002). This difference was observed probably due to the difference of socio-political context between Nepal and Jordan. In addition, the study done in Jordan had not included the perspectives of clients, so it might be inferred that there had been some potential bias in the response given.

With respect to the perceived effects of the delays in the construction projects held by the respondents, the number one potential effect of the project delays is cost overrun followed by arbitration and so on. Without a doubt, the increase of the cost is most important effect of any delayed projects. It is obvious that as long as the project extends, the greater is the cost involved for the operation of the

project for the longer time. The study was quite comparable to the findings of the study done in Jordan where the important effect identified was time overrun, followed by cost overrun and least important being total abandonment of the project (Odeh and Battaineh, 2002).

Extension of Time

The Projects under study has been awarded by National Competitive bidding (NCB) to the national contractors. All projects under study are small to medium in size. No FIDIC conditions of Contract have been followed in these projects. The conditions of Contract formulated by the Public Procurement Monitoring office have been followed in all these projects.

The Section B of the General Conditions of Contract of the Bidding Document for the Procurement of the Works prepared by Public Procurement Monitoring Office of Nepal (2014) is related to the time control in which clause 26 provides guidelines on the Project Schedule as stated that within the time stated in the SCC, after the date of the Letter of Acceptance, the Contractor has to submit to the Project Manager for approval a Program showing the general methods, arrangements, order, and timing for all the activities in the Works. Sub Clause 26.2 relates to the progress update process which states that update of the program is a program showing the actual progress achieved on each activity and the effect of the progress achieved on the timing of the remaining work, including any changes to the sequence of the activities.

Sub clause 27 is related to the extension of time which states that time can be extended if a Compensation Event occurs or a Variation is issued which makes it impossible for Completion to be achieved by the Intended Completion Date without the Contractor taking steps to accelerate the remaining work, which would cause the Contractor to incur additional cost. It further mentioned that the Employer has to decide whether and by how much to extend the Intended Completion Date within 21 days of the Contractor asking the Project Manager for a decision upon the effect of a Compensation Event or Variation and submitting full supporting information at least 7 days prior to the intended completion date. If the Contractor has failed to give early warning of a delay or has failed to cooperate in dealing with a delay, the delay by this failure shall not be considered in assessing the new Intended Completion Date.

The Section 56 of the Public Procurement Act of Public Procurement Monitoring Office, (2006) has provisioned for the extension of period of procurement contract. It states that if the period of procurement contract is to be inevitably extended due to force majeure, failure of the Public Entity to make available the materials to be made available by it or other reasonable factors, the competent authority may extend the period on the prescribed grounds

upon submission of application by the person obtaining procurement contract.

The stipulated planned completion for all projects under study has already been crossed a long before. However, no any projects has been completed till date. In this regard, there exists three options:

1. Extend the time to complete the Work
2. Provision of Delay Damages
3. Contract Termination

It is to be noted here that all projects under study were delayed due to the reasons other than the Contractors reason. The table 4-15 shows the reasons behind the time overrun and the details of time extensions provided to the contractors:

Major factors causing the time extension were

1. Natural Catastrophes,
2. Land issue, Blockade,
3. Scarcity of the materials and
4. Design changes.

Item numbers (1), (2) and (3) above are considered as force majeure according to the respective contract documents. Item number (4) is also the delay causing events whose ownership lies solely upon the Client. Hence for all above issues, the contractor is liable for time extensions. It is to be noted here that all projects under study have followed the General Conditions of Contract of the Standard bid Document of the public Procurement Monitoring office for Time Schedules and Extensions. The EOT 1 for all projects was granted in accordance with the Section 56 of public procurement act and section 120 of public procurement rule.

The General Conditions of Contract of SBD by PPMO has

Table 14. Time Extensions

No	Projects	Construction Start	Project duration	Status of Project	EOT I	EOT II	Reasons
1	Pokhara Shopping Complex at Srijana Chowk	11/20/2014	14 Months	Structure work is completed but finishing work remaining	6 Months	4 Months	National political scenario, Scarcity of material and drawing change and earth quake
2	Office cum Shopping Complex	8/15/2016	15 Months	Only 5% work is completed			
3	Birgunj Bus Park	2/5/2017	15 Months	Only 35% work is completed	12 Months		Blockage of border, Scarcity of material and earth quake
4	Birendranagar Bus Park	4/1/2016	15 Months	50% work is completed			
5	Reinstatement of Municipal building	12/18/2011	15 Months	Structure work is completed but finishing work remaining	6 Months	18 months	Site Clearance, Scarcity of material, strike, Blockage of boarder etc.
6	Bheemdatt Bus Park	8/10/2016	15 Months	Only 10% work is completed			
7	Biratnagar Bus Terminal	11/23/2016	15 Months	Only 5% work is completed			
8	Nepalgunj Bus Park	3/31/2016	15 Months	20% work is completed			

9	Improvement of meena bazar and drainage	5/10/2010	15 Months	Structure work is completed but finishing work remaining	6 Months	18 months	Land disputes, Site clearance, Scarcity of material strike, made banda, Blockage of boarder etc.
10	Butwal Bus Terminal	5/10/2010	18 months	Structure work is completed but finishing work remaining	7 Months	18 months	Site Clearance, internal disputes, Scarcity of material, strike, Blockage of boarder etc.

clearly stated that the contractors, after commencement of work, must submit the detailed work schedule and the program needs to be updated as stipulated in the documents. On Contrary, the program submitted by the contractor, though the critical path method has been used, is not satisfactory. The major stages of work and the detailed work breakdown structures are missing in initially submitted baseline programs. None of the contractors has submitted the updated program to claim for extension of time.

For EOT 2 of all projects under study, no substantial and responsive reasons have been found so far.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the major factors that affect the performance of the project according to the ranking based on RII value for the perceived view of the client, consultants and the contractors on factors affecting the performance are Design related issues, shortage of materials, Quality related issues, slow decision making, construction methodology, labour supply, payment related issues, site management ,discrepancies in contract documents, flaws in organisational structure, interfaces, productivity, change orders, unforeseen site condition, weather conditions and regulatory changes that affect the overall project performance. Twenty Eight different factors affecting the performance of the project were discussed in form of questionnaire and its effect on running projects has also been observed.

This study revealed material related factor to be one of the most important factors among the other groups for the delays in construction projects since the value of relative importance index is highest in material related factors followed by other factors. This fact indeed holds true for the construction projects as the short of material supply would always have much attribution for delays in construction despite having good planning and coordination ensured. The second important factor being the consultant related factor followed by client related factor and contractor related factor and so on in this study.

With respect to the perceived effects of the delays in the construction projects held by the respondents, the potential effect of the project delay is cost overrun followed by arbitration and so on. Without any doubt, the increase of the cost is most important effect of any delayed projects. It is obvious that as long as the project extends, the greater is the cost involved for the operation of the project for the longer time.

All projects under study have been granted extension of time based on the PPA 2063 and PPR 2064. According to the data available, all projects are found to be delayed due to Natural Catastrophes, Land issue, Blockade, Scarcity of the materials and design changes.

Recommendation

The identified major factors affecting the project performance need to be addressed as far as possible to minimise its effects on the project. Since design related issues was identified as the major delay causing events followed by the shortage of material and quality related issues, these factors need to be addressed seriously. Quality control and quality assurance are also vital. For better quality control, the selection of the well-equipped and experienced contractor is must. Shortage of material, slow decision, discrepancies in contract document is also identified as the major factors. To some extent, shortage of material is 'outside factor' and is not in the hand of either party, however, provision of stock is to be exercised to avoid shortage of materials. Discrepancies in the Contract documents can be mitigated by using professional and experienced consulting services. As far the site management is concerned, it is the obligation of the contractor to manage the handed over site in a proper manner. To address the issues of interface with third party is the liability of contractor in general and therefore adequate measures must be taken to minimise the interface related issues. It is suggested that during the construction stage, the organizational changes and regulatory changes should be avoided or so they should not affect the progress of construction.

The effects should be lessened by dealing with factors leading to the effects. The Cost overrun is most likely in the Projects as a consequence of the time overrun followed by arbitration, litigation, dispute arousal and total abandonment. The time that has to be allocated for the project execution must be rational and shall have to consider some reservations for unforeseen site conditions. The disputes, negotiations and court cases should be solved on time and it is preferred that they should not happen and if they happen then the timely solution should be done. By studying the relationship between effects and factors, we can counter the delays by dealing with factors leading to effects.

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